

Comparative Genomics to Metabolomics in the genus *Nocardia*

Supplemental Material

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time [min]	solvent A [%]	solvent B [%]
0	75	25
3	75	25
6	50	50
11	1	99
20	1	99
25	75	25
30	75	25

Table S 2: gradient for analytical HPLC.

time [min]	solvent A [%]	solvent B [%]
0	75	25
3	75	25
6	50	50
11	1	99
20	1	99
22	75	25
25	75	25

Table S 3: genes considered in autoMLST phylogenetic tree.

protein family	gene	associated function	associated enzyme
TIGR01798	cit_synth_I	Energy metabolism	citrate (Si)-synthase
TIGR00043	TIGR00043	Protein synthesis	rRNA maturation RNase YbeY
TIGR00970	leuA_yeast	Amino acid biosynthesis	2-isopropylmalate synthase
TIGR01855	IMP_synth_hisH	Amino acid biosynthesis	imidazole glycerol phosphate synthase, glutamine amidotransferase subunit
TIGR00115	tig	Protein fate	trigger factor
TIGR00138	rsmG_gidB	Protein synthesis	16S rRNA (guanine(527)-N(7))-methyltransferase RsmG
TIGR01978	sufC	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	FeS assembly ATPase SufC
TIGR02673	FtsE	Cellular processes	cell division ATP-binding protein FtsE
TIGR00338	serB	Amino acid biosynthesis	phosphoserine phosphatase SerB
TIGR00154	ispE	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	4-(cytidine 5'-diphospho)-2-C-methyl-D-erythritol kinase
TIGR00031	UDP-GALP_mutase	Cell envelope	UDP-galactopyranose mutase
TIGR00922	nusG	Transcription	transcription termination/antitermination factor NusG
TIGR02091	glgC	Energy metabolism	glucose-1-phosphate adenyltransferase
TIGR03723	T6A_TsaD_YgjD	Protein synthesis	tRNA threonylcarbamoyl adenosine modification protein TsaD
TIGR00158	L9	Protein synthesis	ribosomal protein bl9
TIGR01083	nth	DNA metabolism	endonuclease III
TIGR00090	rsfS_ojap_ybeB	Protein synthesis	ribosome silencing factor
TIGR00091	TIGR00091	Protein synthesis	tRNA (guanine-N(7))-methyltransferase
TIGR02692	tRNA_CCA_actino	Protein synthesis	CCA tRNA nucleotidyltransferase
TIGR01072	murA	Cell envelope	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 1-carboxyvinyltransferase
TIGR00190	thiC	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	phosphomethylpyrimidine synthase
TIGR00096	TIGR00096	Protein synthesis	16S rRNA (cytidine(1402)-2'-O)-methyltransferase
TIGR00218	manA	Energy metabolism	mannose-6-phosphate isomerase, class I
TIGR01737	FGAM_synth_I	Purines, pyrimidines, nucleosides, and nucleotides	phosphoribosylformylglycinamide synthase I
TIGR01994	SUF_scaf_2	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	SUF system FeS assembly protein, NifU family
TIGR03800	PLP_synth_Pdx2	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	pyridoxal 5'-phosphate synthase, glutaminase subunit Pdx2
TIGR00963	secA	Protein fate	preprotein translocase, SecA subunit
TIGR00964	secE_bact	Protein fate	preprotein translocase, SecE subunit
Ribosomal_L10	PF00466.16	Unclassified	Ribosomal protein L10
TIGR01280	xseB	DNA metabolism	exodeoxyribonuclease VII, small subunit
TIGR00168	infC	Protein synthesis	translation initiation factor IF-3
TIGR00731	bl25_bact_ctc	Protein synthesis	ribosomal protein bl25, Ctc-form
TIGR02727	MTHFS_bact	Central intermediary metabolism	5-formyltetrahydrofolate cyclo-ligase
TIGR01966	RNasePH	Transcription	ribonuclease PH
TIGR00382	clpX	Protein fate	ATP-dependent Clp protease, ATP-binding subunit ClpX
TIGR01357	aroB	Amino acid biosynthesis	3-dehydroquinate synthase
TIGR02729	Obg_CgtA	Protein synthesis	Obg family GTPase CgtA
TIGR01683	thiS	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	thiamine biosynthesis protein ThiS
TIGR00020	prfB	Protein synthesis	peptide chain release factor 2
TIGR00751	menA	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	1,4-dihydroxy-2-naphthoate octaprenyltransferase
TIGR03534	RF_mod_PrmC	Protein fate	protein-(glutamine-N5) methyltransferase, release factor-specific
TIGR01393	lepA	Unknown function	elongation factor 4
TIGR00564	trpE_most	Amino acid biosynthesis	anthranilate synthase component I
TIGR00759	aceE	Unclassified	pyruvate dehydrogenase (acetyl-transferring), homodimeric type
TIGR00302	TIGR00302	Purines, pyrimidines, nucleosides, and nucleotides	phosphoribosylformylglycinamide synthase, purS protein
TIGR00330	glpX	Energy metabolism	fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase, class II
TIGR00237	xseA	DNA metabolism	exodeoxyribonuclease VII, large subunit
TIGR00613	reco	DNA metabolism	DNA repair protein RecO
TIGR01498	folK	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-hydroxymethylidihydropteridine diphosphokinase
TIGR00713	hemL	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	glutamate-1-semialdehyde-2,1-aminomutase
TIGR00525	folB	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	dihydroneopterin aldolase
TIGR00615	recR	DNA metabolism	recombination protein RecR
TIGR00362	DnaA	DNA metabolism	chromosomal replication initiator protein DnaA
TIGR01980	sufB	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers	FeS assembly protein SufB
TIGR01051	topA_bact	DNA metabolism	DNA topoisomerase I
TIGR00082	rbfA	Transcription	ribosome-binding factor A
TIGR01039	atpD	Energy metabolism	ATP synthase F1, beta subunit
TIGR00739	yajC	Protein fate	preprotein translocase, YajC subunit
TIGR03284	thym_sym	Purines, pyrimidines, nucleosides, and nucleotides	thymidylate synthase
TIGR01137	cysta_beta	Amino acid biosynthesis	cystathionine beta-synthase
TIGR00103	DNA_YbaB_EbFC	Unknown function	DNA-binding protein, YbaB/EbFC family
TIGR01032	rplT_bact	Protein synthesis	ribosomal protein bl20
TIGR01296	asd_B	Amino acid biosynthesis	aspartate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase

Table S 4: A-domain analysis of NRPS gene encoded in GCF 4.

GCF 4	A1	AA	A2	AA	A3	AA	A4	AA
<i>N. farcinica</i>	DVWHFSXX	S	DALFIGMV	-	DALFMGAI	F/W	DALFLGVI	Hpg
<i>N. brasiliensis</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DALFMGGI	F/W	DALALGVI	Hpg
<i>N. abscessus</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DALFMGVV	F/W	?	?
<i>N. otitidiscaviarum</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DAFFMGGV	L/I/V	DALFLGVI	Hpg
<i>N. kruczakiae</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DALFMGGI	F/W	DALFLGVI	Hpg
<i>N. asteroides</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DVLFMGAV	-	DGLFLGVI	L
<i>N. brevicatena</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFMGMV	-	DALFMGVI	F/W	DALFLGAI	F/W
<i>N. nova</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DALFMGGI	F/W	DALFLGVI	Hpg
<i>N. cyriacigeorgica</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFMGMV	-	DALFMGVV	F/W	DALALGVI	Hpg
<i>N. transvalensis</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DAFFVGGV	V	DALFLGVI	Hpg
<i>N. veterana</i>	DVWHFSLV	S	DALFIGMV	-	DALFMGGI	F/W	DALFLGVI	Hpg

Table S 5: MS properties of terpenibactin A, B and C produced by *Nocardia terpenica* IFM 0406.

name	exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
Terpenibactin A	815.50444	882.41383	882.4135	0.37397
Terpenibactin B	841.52009	908.42948	908.4282	1.40903
Terpenibactin C	843.53574	910.44513	910.4442	1.02148

Table S 6: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135.

exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
745.4262	812.33558	812.3379	2.85597
757.4262	824.33558	824.3353	0.33967
773.4575	840.36688	840.3669	0.02379
771.4418	838.35123	838.3508	0.51291
785.4575	852.36688	852.3668	0.09386

Table S 7: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia takedensis* NBRC 100417.

exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M- 2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M- 2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
771.44184	838.35123	838.3511	0.15507
773.45749	840.36688	840.3657	1.40415
787.47314	854.38253	854.3817	0.97146
801.48879	868.39818	868.3977	0.55274

Table S 8: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia jejuensis* NBRC 103114.

name	exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
	743.41054	810.32047	810.3201	0.4566
	745.42619	812.33612	812.336	0.14772
	771.44184	838.35177	838.3499	2.2306
Nocardimicin G	773.45749	840.36742	840.3676	0.21419

Table S 9: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia fusca* NBRC 14340.

exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M- 2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M- 2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
731.41054	798.31993	798.3198	0.16284
745.42619	812.3356	812.3386	3.69304
757.42619	824.33558	824.3362	0.75212
771.44184	838.35123	838.3539	3.18481
801.48879	868.3982	868.3987	0.57577
815.50444	882.4138	882.4138	0.79327

Table S 10: MS properties of putative siderophore produced by *Nocardia rhamnosiphila* NBRC 108938.

exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
745.42619	812.33558	812.3352	0.46778

Table S 11: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia vermiculata* NBRC 100427.

exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
745.42619	812.33558	812.335	0.71399
771.44184	838.35123	838.3535	2.7077
773.45749	840.36688	840.3685	1.92772
801.48879	868.39818	868.3961	2.39521

Table S 12: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *N. gamkensis* NBRC 108242.

name	exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
	715.37924	782.28863	782.2887	0.08948
	729.39489	796.30428	796.3024	2.36090
	741.39489	808.30428	808.304	0.34640
Formobactin	743.41054	810.31993	810.3192	0.77747
	745.35342	812.26280	812.2634	0.73868
	757.42619	824.33558	824.3355	0.09705
	773.38472	840.29410	840.2954	1.54710

Table S 13: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia elegans* NBRC 108235.

name	exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
	731.41054	798.31993	798.3231	3.97082
	759.44184	826.35123	826.3531	2.26296
Nocardimicin G	773.45749	840.36688	840.3683	1.68974
Nocardimicin H	801.48879	868.39818	868.3985	0.36850

Table S 14: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234.

name	exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
Nocardimicin A	729.39489	796.30428	796.3046	0.27628
	743.41054	810.31993	810.3227	2.75200
	755.41054	822.31993	822.3221	1.98220
Nocardimicin B	757.42619	824.33558	824.3355	0.75212
	771.44184	838.35123	838.3512	0.03578
Nocardimicin D	785.45749	852.3669	852.3668	0.09386
	813.48879	880.39818	880.3982	0.59064
	827.50444	894.41383	894.4131	1.41993

Table S 15: MS properties of putative siderophores produced by *Nocardia cyriacigeorgica* GUH-2.

name	exact mass [M] calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ calculated	exact mass [M-2H+Ga] ⁺ observed	ppm error
	717.39489	784.30428	784.3044	0.15300
	743.41054	810.31993	810.3187	1.51791
	745.42619	812.33558	812.335	0.71399
	759.44184	826.35123	826.3516	0.44775
	773.45749	840.36688	840.3669	0.02380
	799.47314	866.38253	866.3818	0.84258
Brasilibactin A	801.48879	868.39818	868.3989	0.82911

Table S 16: PCR Primers.

Primer name	Primer sequence 5' → 3'
27F	AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG
1492R	GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT

Table S 17: NMR spectroscopic data of a mycobactin-like siderophore from *N. araoensis* NBRC 100135.

Mycobactin-like siderophore incubated with gallium sulphate in CD₃OD, concentrated *in vacuo*, then NMR data recorded in CDCl₃. Numbering scheme adapted from Hoshino et al. 2011.¹

<u>Assignment</u>	<u>¹H-NMR</u>	<u>¹³C-NMR</u>	<u>Number</u>
phenol			
H-3	6.59	115.4	3
H-4	7.32	135.9	4
H-5	6.92	122.8	5
H-6	7.60	129.6	6
oxazoline			
H-9	4.84, 4.61	70.7	9
H-10	4.62	66.8	10
Lys1 (linear)			
NH	7.95	-	13
α	4.69	50.3	14
β	2.13	30.3	28
γ	1.32	29.8	29
δ	2.00, 1.87	27.3	30
ε	4.04, 3.84	53.4	31
3-hydroxybutanoate			
α	2.82, 2.45	41.8	18
β	5.50	67.6	17
γ	1.38	18.4	33
Lys2 (cyclic)			
NH	9.75	-	20
α	4.32	53.7	21
β	2.12, 2.09	26.6	27
γ	1.87, 1.55	27.1	26
δ	1.82, 1.57	18.3	25
ε	3.96, 3.74	48.4	24
Fatty acid			
C=O	-	165.1	1'
H-2'	2.49, 2.33	29.5	2'

H-3'	1.78	25.7	3'
H-4' to H-11'	1.29 (multiple)	29.8 (multiple)	4'-11'
H-12'	1.27	32.1	12'
H-13'	1.30	22.8	13'
H-14'	0.89	14.1	14'

Table S 18: Gene cluster table of nocobactin-like BGC from *N. araoensis* NBRC 100135.

gene	AA	protein homolog	accession number	ID	predicted function
<i>nbtS</i>	436	salicylate synthase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55464.1	87.7	salicylate synthase
<i>nbtT</i>	538	putative salicylate-AMP ligase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55465.1	84.56	salicylate-AMP ligase
<i>nbtG</i>	428	putative lysine-N-oxygenase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55606.1	79.43	lysine-N-oxygenase
<i>nbtH</i>	220	putative N6-hydroxylysine acetyltransferase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55607.1	58.41	N6-hydroxylysine acetyltransferase
<i>nbtA</i>	257	thioesterase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55608.1	62.55	thioesterase
<i>nbtB</i>	442	putative polyketide synthase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55609.1	72.54	polyketide synthase
<i>nbtC</i>	1011	putative polyketide synthase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55610.1	55.11	polyketide synthase
<i>nbtD</i>	1508	non-ribosomal peptide synthetase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55612.1	58.6	non-ribosomal peptide synthetase
<i>nbtE</i>	1671	putative non-ribosomal peptide synthetase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55611.1	57.22	non-ribosomal peptide synthetase
<i>nbtX</i>	360	putative membrane protein [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD60682.1	35.82	Unknown/ hypothetical protein
<i>nbtF</i>	958	putative non-ribosomal peptide synthetase [<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152]	BAD55613.1	81.31	non-ribosomal peptide synthetase

*Abbreviations

AA protein length in amino acid

ID amino acid identity [%]

Sim amino acid similarity

N. *Nocardia*

Table S 19: *Nocardia* strains used for metabolic analysis.

genome	GenBank accession number	Source of Isolation	Biosafety level
<i>Nocardia araoensis</i> NBRC 100135	BAFR00000000	Human	1
<i>Nocardia cyriaciageorgica</i> GUH-2	NC_016887	human	2
<i>Nocardia takedensis</i> NBRC 100417	NZ_BAGG00000000	Human	1
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. Root136	NZ_LMFE00000000	Soil	1
<i>Nocardia jejuensis</i> NBRC 103114	NZ_BDBU00000000	Human	1
<i>Nocardia fusca</i> NBRC 14340	NZ_BDCU00000000	Freshwater	1
<i>Nocardia rhamnosiphila</i> NBRC 108938	NZ_BDCL00000000	Animal	1
<i>Nocardia vermiculata</i> NBRC 100427	NZ_BDCA00000000	Soil	1
<i>Nocardia gamkensis</i> NBRC 108242	NZ_BDBM00000000	Soil	1
<i>Nocardia elegans</i> NBRC 108235	NZ_BDBF00000000	Human	1
<i>Nocardia alba</i> NBRC 108234	NZ_BDAX00000000	plant	1
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> DSM 44129	n.a.	animal	1

Table S 20: checkM analysis on *Nocardia* genomes used in this study.

bin id	marker lineage	# markers	# marker sets	completeness	contamination	strain heterogeneity	number of contigs
<i>Nocardia abscessus</i> NBRC_100374	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	1.69	0	274
<i>Nocardia acidivorans</i> NBRC_108247	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.56	2.43	7.14	161
<i>Nocardia africana</i> NBRC_100379	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.37	1.32	15.38	93
<i>Nocardia alba</i> NBRC_108234	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	98.96	2.07	0	62
<i>Nocardia altamirensis</i> NBRC_108246	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	4.19	7.14	166
<i>Nocardia amamiensis</i> NBRC_102102	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.09	6.31	2.7	487
<i>Nocardia amikacinintolerans</i> DSM_45535	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	0.89	0	33
<i>Nocardia amikacinintolerans</i> DSM_45536	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	1.12	0	28
<i>Nocardia amikacinintolerans</i> DSM_45537	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	0.93	0	95
<i>Nocardia amikacinintolerans</i> DSM_45538	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	0.93	0	30
<i>Nocardia amikacinintolerans</i> NBRC_108937	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.56	1.03	0	108
<i>Nocardia anaemiae</i> NBRC_100462	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	2.51	18.18	134
<i>Nocardia aobensis</i> NBRC_100429	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.81	1.04	15.38	291
<i>Nocardia araoensis</i> NBRC_100135	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.44	2.16	11.76	352
<i>Nocardia arthritidis</i> NBRC_100137	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.62	1.1	0	113
<i>Nocardia asiatica</i> NBRC_100129	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	4.35	10.34	475
<i>Nocardia asteroides</i> DSM_43373	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.75	1.74	9.09	25
<i>Nocardia asteroides</i> NBRC_15531	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.37	2.11	16.67	39
<i>Nocardia beijingensis</i> NBRC_16342	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.62	1.95	0	113
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i> ATCC_700358	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	4.84	10	1
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i> IFM_10947	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	4.84	10	223
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i> NBRC_14402	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	3.66	8.82	128
<i>Nocardia brevitatena</i> NBRC_12119	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.25	2.71	18.18	243
<i>Nocardia calshijiensis</i> NBRC_108228	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	98.43	0.86	0	60
<i>Nocardia carnea</i> NBRC_14403	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.32	1.48	0	126
<i>Nocardia cerraensis</i> NBRC_101014	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.85	1.17	16.67	388
<i>Nocardia concava</i> NBRC_100430	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.76	4.41	0	206
<i>Nocardia couleae</i> NBRC_108252	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	98.81	2.13	0	40
<i>Nocardia crassostreae</i> strain NBRC_100342	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.51	2.6	9.52	57
<i>Nocardia cummideiensis</i> NBRC_100378	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	1.65	0	60
<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i> GH-2	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	0.39	0	1
<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i> NBRC_100375	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	98.25	1	11.11	328
<i>Nocardia donostiensis</i> strain X1655	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.25	0.56	0	49
<i>Nocardia elegans</i> NBRC_108235	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.2	1.63	0	117
<i>Nocardia exalbida</i> NBRC_100660	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.69	1.11	8.33	165
<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> DSM_43257	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.87	0.9	25	43
<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM_10152	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.87	0.3	28.57	3
<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> NCTC_11134	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	1.24	20	5
<i>Nocardia flavorosea</i> NBRC_108225	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.32	0.5	0	70
<i>Nocardia fluminea</i> DSM_44489	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	2.49	12.5	4
<i>Nocardia fusca</i> NBRC_14340	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.29	3.06	0	105
<i>Nocardia gamkensis</i> NBRC_108242	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.62	1.39	9.09	120
<i>Nocardia grenadensis</i> NBRC_108939	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.32	2.25	52	71
<i>Nocardia harenae</i> NBRC_108248	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.15	1.07	0	25
<i>Nocardia higoensis</i> NBRC_100133	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.69	1.03	0	185
<i>Nocardia ignorata</i> NBRC_108230	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	98.43	2.22	0	69
<i>Nocardia inohanensis</i> NBRC_100128	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.46	2.1	0	26
<i>Nocardia jejuensis</i> NBRC_103114	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.75	1.55	0	89
<i>Nocardia jiangxiensis</i> NBRC_101359	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.94	2.95	5.26	163
<i>Nocardia jinanensis</i> NBRC_108249	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	63.75	0.63	0	107
<i>Nocardia kruzakiae</i> NBRC_101016	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.99	1.7	11.11	103
<i>Nocardia lijiangensis</i> NBRC_108240	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.23	1.14	0	230
<i>Nocardia mexicana</i> NBRC_108244	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.24	2.63	10	180
<i>Nocardia mikamii</i> NBRC_108933	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.99	1.91	0	42
<i>Nocardia miyuenensis</i> NBRC_108239	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.67	3.14	4.35	208
<i>Nocardia nilgatensis</i> NBRC_100131	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.65	2.65	4.17	114
<i>Nocardia niwae</i> NBRC_108934	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.81	1.58	7.69	105
<i>Nocardia nova</i> SH22a NONO	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.37	0.86	0	1
<i>Nocardia otitidiscaeviarum</i> IFM_11049	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.29	1.63	5.26	65
<i>Nocardia otitidiscaeviarum</i> NBRC_14405	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.29	1.61	8.33	239
<i>Nocardia paucivorans</i> NBRC_100373	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	98.87	0.78	0	128
<i>Nocardia pneumoniae</i> NBRC_100136	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.44	1.65	8.33	150
<i>Nocardia pseudobrasiliensis</i> IFM_0761	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	96.62	3.51	15.38	204
<i>Nocardia pseudovaccinii</i> NBRC_100343	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	4.77	16.67	492
<i>Nocardia puris</i> NBRC_108233	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.32	2.99	0	175
<i>Nocardia rhamnosiphila</i> NBRC_108938	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.32	1.44	15.79	93
<i>Nocardia salmonicida</i> NBRC_13393	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.81	3.36	11.76	99
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> N-2927	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.81	2.81	0	593
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> U-1	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.61	2.81	0	313
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> ZJ0503	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.81	2.62	0	319
<i>Nocardia shimofuensis</i> NBRC_100134	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.69	0.75	0	75
<i>Nocardia sienata</i> NBRC_100364	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.29	1.39	4.76	135
<i>Nocardia soli</i> NBRC_100376	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.56	1.72	0	111
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 348MFTsu.1	o Actinomycetales (UID1814)	572	276	99.31	0.38	0	35
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 852002-20019 SCH5090214	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.99	2.13	20	467
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 852002-51101 SCH5132738	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.37	1.07	18.18	217
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 852002-51244 SCH5132740	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.37	1.44	16.67	297
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. BMG_111209	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.75	1.29	0	5
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. BMG_51109	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.37	2.28	12.5	4
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. CNS044	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	1.51	14.29	13
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. CNY236	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	98.62	1.63	0	75
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. LAM0056	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.37	0.76	0	5
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. NRRL_3-836	o Actinomycetales (UID1746)	368	206	99.51	1.53	0	188
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. NRRL_WC-3656	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.99	1.17	29.41	152
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. Root136	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.81	1.9	0	14
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. W9405	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.31	3.08	0	110
<i>Nocardia spelunca</i> NBRC_108251	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.32	0.54	0	61
<i>Nocardia takedensis</i> NBRC_100417	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.51	3.41	4.35	265
<i>Nocardia tenerifensis</i> NBRC_101015	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	98.88	4.46	15.62	615
<i>Nocardia terpenica</i> IFM_0406	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.37	5.84	10	21
<i>Nocardia terpenica</i> NBRC_100888	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	90.51	11.47	6.94	1
<i>Nocardia testacea</i> NBRC_100365	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	98.94	1.79	21.74	271
<i>Nocardia thailandica</i> NBRC_100428	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.18	3.3	0	312
<i>Nocardia transversalis</i> NBRC_15921	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	572	265	99.18	3.3	0	128
<i>Nocardia uniformis</i> NBRC_13702	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.67	2.05	0	144
<i>Nocardia vaccinii</i> NBRC_15922	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.48	2.33	0	131
<i>Nocardia vermiculata</i> NBRC_100427	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.99	0.28	0	80
<i>Nocardia veterana</i> NBRC_100344	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	99.37	1.01	50	210
<i>Nocardia vinacea</i> NBRC_16497	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.09	4.37	14.29	429
<i>Nocardia violaceofusca</i> NBRC_14427	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	571	265	98.96	0.5	10	77
<i>Nocardia vulneris</i> W9851	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.75	3.84	8.82	137
<i>Nocardia xishanensis</i> NBRC_101358	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	574	266	99.56	2.22	0	124
<i>Nocardia yamanshiensis</i> NBRC_100130	o Actinomycetales (UID1815)	567	264	99.62	3.06	5	80

Table S 21: Analysis of putative virulence factors in *Nocardia* spp..

Genes for catalases and superoxide dismutases were manually searched by hmmsearch (HMMER 3.1b2). Catalases included searches for Catalase, Mn_catalase Catalase-rel, Catalase_C, HTHP and Peroxidase Hidden Markov Models. Superoxide Dismutases (SoDs) included searches for Sod_Cu, Sod_Fe_C, Sod_Fe_N and Sod_Ni Hidden Markov Models. Virulence factor counts were in accordance with Vera-Cabrera *et al.* 2013.²

strain	source of isolation	catalases	SoDs	number of BGCs	autoMLST clade	genome size [Mbp]
<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv	human	1	2	15	n.a.	4.4
<i>Nocardia abscessus</i> NBRC 100374	human	5	2	46	A	8.4
<i>Nocardia acidovorans</i> NBRC 108247	soil	3	2	37	F	7.6
<i>Nocardia africana</i> NBRC 100379	human	6	2	30	F	7.8
<i>Nocardia alba</i> NBRC 108234	soil	3	2	32	D	7.3
<i>Nocardia altamirensis</i> NBRC 108246	soil	n.a.	n.a.	57	A	9.8
<i>Nocardia amamiensis</i> NBRC 102102	soil	3	2	45	A	8.2
<i>Nocardia amikacinotolerans</i> DSM 45535	human	3	2	32	B	7.3
<i>Nocardia amikacinotolerans</i> DSM 45536	human	4	2	30	B	7.5
<i>Nocardia amikacinotolerans</i> DSM 45537	human	4	2	31	B	7.4
<i>Nocardia amikacinotolerans</i> DSM 45538	human	4	2	31	B	7.6
<i>Nocardia amikacinotolerans</i> NBRC 108937	human	4	2	30	B	7.6
<i>Nocardia anaeimae</i> NBRC 100462	human	5	2	46	A	8.6
<i>Nocardia abensis</i> NBRC 100429	human	4	2	43	E	7.5
<i>Nocardia arvensis</i> NBRC 100135	human	4	2	45	A	7.7
<i>Nocardia arthritis</i> NBRC 100137	human	5	2	44	A	7.1
<i>Nocardia asiatica</i> NBRC 100129	human	5	2	56	A	8.5
<i>Nocardia asteroides</i> DSM 43373	human	3	2	30	D	7.0
<i>Nocardia asteroides</i> NBRC 15531	soil	3	2	30	D	7.0
<i>Nocardia beijingensis</i> NBRC 16342	soil	4	2	43	A	7.5
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i> ATCC 700358	human	5	2	49	A	9.4
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i> IFM 10847	human	5	2	56	A	9.2
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i> NBRC 14402	human	6	2	49	A	8.9
<i>Nocardia brevicatenata</i> NBRC 12119	human	3	2	35	C	7.0
<i>Nocardia caishijensis</i> NBRC 108228	soil	2	2	28	D	6.3
<i>Nocardia carneae</i> NBRC 14403	human	3	2	29	C	7.5
<i>Nocardia cerasioides</i> NBRC 101014	soil	5	2	50	F	7.6
<i>Nocardia concava</i> NBRC 100430	human	4	2	51	F	8.9
<i>Nocardia couleae</i> NBRC 108252	soil	3	2	31	D	6.6
<i>Nocardia crassostreae</i> NBRC 100342	animal	3	2	41	F	8.3
<i>Nocardia cummideiensis</i> NBRC 100378	plant	3	2	30	D	7.5
<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i> GUH-2	human	3	2	22	C	6.2
<i>Nocardia cyriacigeorgica</i> NBRC 100375	human	4	3	35	C	6.3
<i>Nocardia donostiensis</i> X1655	human	4	2	29	C	5.8
<i>Nocardia elegans</i> NBRC 108235	human	3	2	36	E	7.5
<i>Nocardia exalida</i> NBRC 100660	human	5	2	44	A	7.4
<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> DSM 43257	human	5	2	23	B	6.4
<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> IFM 10152	human	4	2	17	B	6.3
<i>Nocardia farcinica</i> NCTC 11134	animal	5	2	19	B	6.5
<i>Nocardia flavovaseae</i> NBRC 108225	soil	3	3	25	C	7.4
<i>Nocardia fluminea</i> DSM 44489	freshwater	2	2	32	D	8.1
<i>Nocardia fusca</i> NBRC 14340	soil	4	2	32	C	8.0
<i>Nocardia gamkensis</i> NBRC 108242	soil	4	2	37	A	7.7
<i>Nocardia grenadensis</i> NBRC 108939	soil	3	2	29	C	6.5
<i>Nocardia harense</i> NBRC 108248	soil	3	2	26	X	6.1
<i>Nocardia higoensis</i> NBRC 100133	human	2	2	28	B	7.0
<i>Nocardia ignarata</i> NBRC 108230	human	3	2	32	D	7.0
<i>Nocardia imohansensis</i> NBRC 100128	human	6	2	42	F	8.1
<i>Nocardia lianyuensis</i> NBRC 101359	soil	5	3	38	E	10.4
<i>Nocardia linensis</i> NBRC 108249	soil	4	3	29	C	5.0
<i>Nocardia kruszchiae</i> NBRC 101016	human	4	2	36	E	7.3
<i>Nocardia lijiangensis</i> NBRC 108240	soil	4	2	47	B	8.2
<i>Nocardia mexicana</i> NBRC 108244	human	4	2	43	E	9.0
<i>Nocardia mikamii</i> NBRC 108933	human	4	2	36	E	7.6
<i>Nocardia miyuenensis</i> NBRC 108239	soil	9	2	41	E	10.5
<i>Nocardia niigatensis</i> NBRC 100131	human	4	2	33	F	8.2
<i>Nocardia niwaensis</i> NBRC 108934	human	4	2	40	A	7.3
<i>Nocardia nova</i> SH22a	plant	3	2	30	E	8.3
<i>Nocardia otitidiscaviarum</i> IFM 11049	human	5	3	31	F	7.9
<i>Nocardia otitidiscaviarum</i> NBRC 14405	animal	6	3	33	F	7.5
<i>Nocardia pouvairensis</i> NBRC 100373	human	5	2	30	C	6.0
<i>Nocardia pneumoniae</i> NBRC 100136	human	4	2	41	A	7.6
<i>Nocardia pseudobrasiliensis</i> IFM 0761	human	4	3	51	E	8.3
<i>Nocardia pseudovaccinii</i> NBRC 100343	soil	4	2	56	A	9.9
<i>Nocardia puris</i> NBRC 108233	human	3	2	38	B	7.7
<i>Nocardia rhamnosiphila</i> NBRC 108938	soil	3	2	40	C	7.7
<i>Nocardia salmonicida</i> NBRC 13393	animal	3	2	33	D	8.3
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> N-2927	animal	2	2	36	F	7.7
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> U-1	animal	2	2	30	F	7.7
<i>Nocardia seriolae</i> ZJ0503	animal	2	2	31	F	7.7
<i>Nocardia shimizuensis</i> NBRC 100134	soil	2	2	23	B	6.3
<i>Nocardia sinensis</i> NBRC 100364	human	4	2	38	C	6.8
<i>Nocardia soil</i> NBRC 100376	freshwater	3	2	32	D	7.6
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 852002-20019_SCH5090214	?	4	2	35	E	8.3
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 852002-51101_SCH5132738	?	4	2	35	E	7.7
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. 852002-51244_SCH5132740	?	4	2	36	E	7.7
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. BMG 111209	plant	3	2	29	F	9.1
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. BMG 51109	plant	4	2	45	E	8.8
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. CNS044	marine	5	2	35	B	7.4
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. CNY236	marine	2	2	38	A	5.3
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. NRRL WC-3656	soil	3	2	41	E	7.3
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. Roat136	plant	3	2	30	D	7.3
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. W9805	human	2	2	32	B	7.2
<i>Nocardia spelunceae</i> NBRC 108251	soil	5	2	24	C	7.4
<i>Nocardia takedensis</i> NBRC 100417	soil	3	2	35	B	8.0
<i>Nocardia tenerifensis</i> NBRC 101015	soil	5	3	71	A	9.7
<i>Nocardia terpenica</i> IFM 0406	human	4	2	48	E	9.3
<i>Nocardia terpenica</i> NBRC 100888	human	4	2	18	E	8.6
<i>Nocardia testacea</i> NBRC 100365	human	4	2	29	C	7.3
<i>Nocardia thailandica</i> NBRC 100428	human	3	2	33	D	6.8
<i>Nocardia transvalensis</i> NBRC 15921	human	4	2	36	D	8.4
<i>Nocardia uniformis</i> NBRC 13702	soil	4	2	36	F	8.8
<i>Nocardia vaccinii</i> NBRC 15922	plant	3	2	31	E	9.2
<i>Nocardia vermiculata</i> NBRC 103427	human	4	2	28	E	6.7
<i>Nocardia veterana</i> NBRC 100344	human	4	2	29	E	6.8
<i>Nocardia vinacea</i> NBRC 16497	soil	6	2	61	A	10.2
<i>Nocardia violaceofusca</i> NBRC 14427	soil	4	2	35	E	7.5
<i>Nocardia vulneris</i> W9851	human	6	2	46	A	9.3
<i>Nocardia xishanensis</i> NBRC 101358	soil	5	2	27	B	7.7
<i>Nocardia yamanashiensis</i> NBRC 100130	human	3	2	49	F	9.1
<i>Nocardia jejuensis</i> NBRC 103114	soil	4	2	37	F	8.7
<i>Nocardia</i> sp. LAM0056	soil	3	2	22	C	6.2

Table S 22: Presence/absence map of *N. farcinica* IFM 10152 BGCs in group 1 pathogens.

Putative antiSMASH (4.0.0) BGCs from *Nocardia farcinica* IFM 10152 were used as reference to manually analyze the BGC content of the other group 1 *Nocardia* strains. Presence/ absence in other *Nocardia* was marked in color, when a homologous BGC was found. Color indicates BGC cluster types: Light yellow (type I pks), dark blue (other), purple (terpene), dark green (nrps), dark yellow (arylpolyene), light green (ectoine), light blue (type I pks-nrps).

group 1 pathogen	antiSMASH 4.0.0 predicted BGCs																			
	1	2	3a	3b	3c	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16a	16b	16c
<i>N. farcinica</i> IFM 10152	Light yellow	Dark blue	Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow	Dark blue	Light green	Dark green	Light blue	Dark green	Purple	Light yellow	Purple	Light yellow	Light blue	Dark green	Dark green
<i>N. cyriaciageorgica</i> GUH-2	Light yellow	Dark blue	Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow		Light green			Dark green		Light yellow			Light blue	Dark green	Dark green
<i>N. asteroides</i> NBRC 15531	Light yellow	Dark blue	Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow		Light green			Dark green	Purple	Light yellow			Light blue	Dark green	Dark green
<i>N. nova</i> SH22a	Light yellow		Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow		Light green			Dark green		Light yellow			Light blue	Dark green	Dark green
<i>N. otitidiscaviarum</i> NBRC 14405	Light yellow		Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow		Light green			Dark green		Light yellow			Light blue	Dark green	Dark green
<i>N. abscessus</i> NBRC 100374	Light yellow	Dark blue	Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow		Light green			Dark green	Purple	Light yellow			Light blue	Dark green	Dark green
<i>N. brasiliensis</i> IFM 10847	Light yellow	Dark blue	Purple	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green	Purple	Dark yellow		Light green			Dark green	Purple	Light yellow			Light blue	Dark green	Dark green

Figures

Figure S 1: Genome size plotted against the number of predicted BGCs in *Nocardia* strains.

Each dot corresponds to one *Nocardia* strain. Colors indicate phylogenetic clade A-F and X. Trendline indicates a positive correlation between number of BGCs present in a strain and its genome size (coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.4057$)).

Figure S 2: *Nocardia* maximum likelihood autoMLST tree.

Analysis of 104 genomes obtained from JGI specified as *Nocardia* based on 63 concatenated housekeeping genes identified with autoMLST. Ultrafast bootstrap values were calculated using 1000 replicates. *Mycobacterium fallax* DSM 44179 and *Gordonia bronchialis* DSM 43247 were used as outgroups.

Figure S 3: Terpenibactins A-C produced by *N. terpenica* IFM 0406.

Figure S 4: MS/MS analysis of terpenibactin A.

Precursor mass (882.4135 [M-2H+Ga]⁺) is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 5: MS/MS analysis of a putative mycobactin-like siderophore with 824.3353 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 6: MS/MS analysis of a putative mycobactin-like siderophore with 840.3669 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 7: MS/MS analysis of 854.3817 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia takedensis* NBRC 100417.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 8: MS/MS analysis of putative nocardimicin G with 840.3676 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia jejuensis* NBRC 103114.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 9: MS/MS analysis of 812.3442 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia fusca* NBRC 14340.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 10: MS/MS analysis of 812.3352 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia ramosiphila* NBRC 108938. Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 11: MS/MS analysis of 840.3685 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia vermiculata* NBRC 100427.
Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 12: MS/MS analysis of putative formobactin with 810.3192 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia gamkensis* NBRC 108242.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 13: MS/MS analysis of putative carboxynocobactin with 812.2634 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia gamkensis* NBRC 108242. Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 14: MS/MS analysis of putative carboxynocobactin with 840.2954 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia gamkensis* NBRC 108242. Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 15: MS/MS analysis of putative nocardimicin G with 840.3683 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia elegans* NBRC 108235.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 16: MS/MS analysis of putative nocardimicin H with 868.3985 $[\text{M}-2\text{H}+\text{Ga}]^+$ produced by *Nocardia elegans* NBRC 108235.
Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 17 MS/MS analysis of 810.3227 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234.
Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 18: MS/MS analysis of putative nocardimicin A with 796.3046 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 19: MS/MS analysis of putative nocardimicin B with 824.3355 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 20: MS/MS analysis of putative nocardimicin D with 852.3668 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ produced by *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 21: MS/MS analysis of putative brasilibactin A with 868.3989 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$ produced by *Nocardia cyriacigeorgica* GUH-2.

Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 22: BiG-SCAPE cluster-type sequence similarity network of all *nocobactin*-type BGCs from *Nocardia* strains found with antiSMASH 4.0.

A BiG-SCAPE threshold of 70 % is shown without singletons. Nocobactin-like BGCs and respective cluster parts II (*nbtS/nbtT*) were trimmed manually and concatenated. Bold circles highlighted show strains cultivated for metabolomics studies. Numbers represent strain identification numbers. Filling colors represent phylogenetic clades A-F.

(1) Isotopic peak analysis of 838.3512 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ non-supplemented cultures

(2) Isotopic peak analysis of 839.3540 [M-2H+Ga]⁺ from L-serine-1-¹³C-supplemented cultures

Figure S 23: Isotopic peak analysis of unlabeled and ¹³C-labeled nocobactin-like siderophore.

Isotopic peak analysis of *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234 extracts; (1) unfed *Nocardia alba* produces unlabeled nocobactin-like siderophore 838.3512 [M-2H+Ga]⁺; feeding *Nocardia alba* with ¹³C₁-labeled L-serine results in m/z shifts of 839.3540 [M-2H+Ga+1]⁺, 840.3561 [M-2H+Ga+2]⁺, 841.3546 [M-2H+Ga+3]⁺, 842.3574 [M-2H+Ga+4]⁺, 843.3618 [M-2H+Ga+5]⁺.

(1) MS/MS analysis of an unlabeled nocobactin-like siderophore; precursor ion m/z 838.3608 $[M-2H+Ga]^+$

(2) MS/MS analysis of a L-serine-1- ^{13}C labeled nocobactin-like siderophore; precursor mass ion m/z 839.5489 $[M-2H+Ga+1]^+$

Figure S 24: MS/MS analysis of a ^{13}C -labeled/ unlabeled nocobactin-like siderophore from *Nocardia alba* NBRC 108234.

Labeled ^{13}C is marked in green. Precursor mass is marked with a blue diamond.

Figure S 25: TOCSY correlations and key HMBC correlations of a mycobactin-type siderophore with m/z 840.3669 $[M+Ga-2H]^+$.

Figure S 26: 1H NMR spectrum of a gallium-bound mycobactin-like siderophore with m/z 840.3669 $[M+Ga-2H]^+$ from *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135 in $CDCl_3$ (600 MHz).

Figure S 27: ^1H - ^{13}C multiplicity edited HSQC NMR spectrum of gallium-bound mycobactin-like siderophore from *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135 in CDCl_3 (600 MHz) with m/z 840.3669 $[\text{M}+\text{Ga}-2\text{H}]^+$.

Figure S 28: ^1H - ^1H TOCSY NMR spectrum of gallium-bound mycobactin-like siderophore from *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135 in CDCl_3 (600 MHz) with m/z 840.3669 $[\text{M}+\text{Ga}-2\text{H}]^+$.

Figure S 29: ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR spectrum of gallium-bound mycobactin-like siderophore from *Nocardia araoensis* NBRC 100135 in CDCl_3 (600 MHz) with m/z 840.3669 $[\text{M}+\text{Ga}-2\text{H}]^+$.

Figure S 30: *Nocardia* autoMLST tree. Colors indicate *Nocardia* spp. source of isolation. Information regarding isolation source was taken from respective published genomes.

Figure S 31: BiG-SCAPE cluster type sequence similarity network of all BGCs from *Nocardia* strains found with antiSMASH 4.0 including the MIBiG database.

Colors show cluster types from *Nocardia* BGCs. Colorless nodes are hybrid BGCs found in *Nocardia*. Bold node borders refer to group 1 pathogens. MIBiG BGCs (version 1.4) were hidden when no *Nocardia* BGC showed a similarity.

Figure S 32: Number of contigs plotted against the number of predicted BGCs in *Nocardia* strains. Each dot corresponds to one *Nocardia* strain. Trendline indicates no correlation between number of BGCs present in a strain and its genome size (coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.2821$)).

Figure S 33: Boxplot of BGC class frequency distribution across *Nocardia* genome groups.

Group1: Group 1 pathogenic *Nocardia*. Other: “other” *Nocardia* in analysis not in group 1 pathogens. X-axis represents BiG-SCAPE groups across *Nocardia* natural product classes. Y-axis represents total numbers of BGC-class frequencies. Black bars within boxplots show median BGC-class frequencies. Black dots represent outliers. Red/blue lines show whiskers of respective groups. Box edges represent lower and upper quartile. For identifying the group 1 individual genome specific clusters, a raw distance (cutoff = 0.75) was used as given in BiG-SCAPE network matrices.

Figure S 34: PCA-analysis on GCF presence/absence.

GCF presence/absence information for clustering the *Nocardia* genomes into separate groups based on clinical annotations (*Nocardia* group 1 pathogens: 1 = *Nocardia abscessus* NBRC 100374; 5 = *Nocardia asteroides* NBRC 15531; 6 = *Nocardia brasiliensis* ATCC 700358; 13 = *Nocardia cyriacigeorgica* GUH-2; 16 = *Nocardia farcinica* IFM 10152; 21 = *Nocardia otitidiscaviarum* NBRC 14405; 47 = *Nocardia nova* SH22a (NONO); “other” *Nocardia* genomes not in group). X and Y axis show principal component 1 (PC1) and principal component 2 (PC2) that explain 3.2 % and 2.6 % of the total variance, respectively. Sample size = 107 data points. Genome analysis IDs are annotated alongside the data points. The PCA plot was performed using ClustVis web tool.

References

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